

HISTORY OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF IRRIGATION SYSTEMS AND THE MELIORATIVE CONDITION OF LANDS IN SOUTHERN KHOREZM IN THE 50s-60s OF THE 20TH CENTURY

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Abstract. The article provides a historical and economic analysis in the South Khorezm oasis during the second half of the 20th century, spanning the 1950s and 1960s, as well as the irrigation and land reclamation processes that were an integral part of it, from a historical and economic perspective. The consequences of the extensive use of regional land and water resources in the context of a centralized planning system aimed at expanding the cotton monoculture and the rice-growing base are revealed. An objective assessment of the impact of the commissioning of the Tuyamuyun Reservoir and administrative-managerial reforms on the region's agro-industrial complex was also conducted.

Keywords: South Khorezm, irrigation, land reclamation, cotton, rice farming, water resources, collector-drainage networks, Tuyamuyun reservoir.

The second half of the 20th century holds a prominent place in the agrarian history of Central Asia, particularly the Lower Amu Darya basin, as a period of radical hydraulic transformations and intensive land resource exploitation. Within the command economy of this period, strategic plans were advanced to transform the republic's agricultural sector, and the South Khorezm region in particular, into a major cotton-producing hub of all-Union importance. However, the predominance of extensive methods, the continuous expansion of arable land, and the unsustainable over-utilization of water resources severely impacted the oasis ecosystem, most notably the meliorative condition of the land. During the 1950s and 1960s, the poor state of hydraulic infrastructure alongside the inadequacy of main canals and collector-drainage networks triggered a rise in groundwater levels and chronic soil salinization across the region. This, in turn, not only undermined agrotechnical efficiency but also significantly hindered the sustainable economic development of the oasis.

The construction of the Chardzhou-Kungrad railway in 1952 – 1955 served to increase the agro-industrial potential of the South Khorezm region, surrounded by the Karakum and Kyzylkum, and its integration with all-Union markets. [2. 120] This transport artery

significantly stimulated regional economic activity, unlocking new opportunities for the spatial allocation of productive forces.

Driven by the Soviet government's agrarian policy, efforts to construct and rehabilitate irrigation canals in the South Khorezm region were intensified from the 1960s onward, mirroring trends across other regions, to ensure the "productive utilization" of the Amu Darya and Syr Darya waters for newly reclaimed lands. [6. 250] Between 1959 and 1969, the state allocated 56 million soums and collective farms contributed 16 million soums for the construction and maintenance of irrigation systems in the region. [3. 2-3] Of course, this was only one of the measures taken to further develop cotton growing in the region.

From a historical and geographical perspective, the Uzbek SSR provided water to approximately 250,000 hectares of sown areas covering the southern districts of the Khorezm region, the Tashkhauz region within the Turkmen SSR, and the Amu Darya district of the Karakalpak ASSR through the Tashsoka, Kilichbay, and Kipchak-Bozsu main canals, which are considered the foundation of the oasis's irrigation system. These large hydraulic structures were built in 1939 – 1941 in accordance with special decrees and instructions of the Soviet government, through mass people's khashars, which were a unique form of agrarian policy of the period, and in a short period of time. [7. 36]

While the irrigation area of the Tashsoka main canal in the region is 186,000 hectares, it actually serves to irrigate 1,900,000 hectares of land, including 120,000 hectares of cotton fields. Furthermore, the construction of Toshsoqa contributed to the water supply of 74,500 hectares of land in the Tashkhauz region. [1. 473]

Metal flood control systems that prevent sedimentation have been built in the Tashsoka, Kilichbay, and Kipchak-Bozsu canals. According to production studies, these systems annually capture up to 1 million m³ of bottom sediment in the canals, which contributes to an increase in the capacity of the canals. [7. 36]

In order to increase the area of cotton cultivation in the region and increase the yield of cotton, the Soviet government tried to use natural resources as much as possible, without taking into account a number of factors. Nevertheless, despite this work, which was carried out on the basis of administrative-command, only 50-60 percent of the work that should have been carried out in the main canals during the leaching of salt before sowing was completed. This had a negative impact on the delay in sowing cotton seeds and the amount of the harvest.

In accordance with agricultural traditions, to obtain an effective cotton harvest, leaching of sown areas and pre-sowing irrigation should be carried out in two periods: 50% in autumn

and 50% in spring. Saline soils in the Khorezm region are often eroded in the spring. Because of the “cotton policy” of the Soviet government, the cotton harvest was delayed until mid-December. As a result, the autumn leaching work was not carried out.

In 1955, irrigator D. D. Atashev put forward an initiative to leach the saline soils of saline sown areas into agricultural production practice on the eve of the end of the autumn growing season (before the cotton harvest is fully collected). This proposal was introduced into the agrotechnical practice of a number of collective farms in the oasis as an experiment. [4. 16-18] However, the proposed practice did not yield the expected economic and reclamation effect due to its incompatibility with the specific nature, soil composition, and climatic conditions of the region.

In accordance with a special decree by the government of the Uzbek SSR dated August 16, 1966, an independent melioration department was established under the Khorezm Regional Water Management Administration on July 1, 1967. This was done to improve the condition of irrigated lands in the region and to achieve high yields from cotton and rice. [8. 3-6]

Water resources in the oasis were primarily used to irrigate cotton fields, which were considered strategic crops for the Union. This, in turn, caused a serious water shortage during the growing season in the grain, vegetable, and horticultural sectors, leading to a lag in the development of these sectors. As a result of such a one-sided distribution system, there were also chronic interruptions in the water supply of the population's private household plots. Furthermore, the obsolescence of the material and technical base of the water management system, the lack of modern hydraulic equipment, and the non-compliance of existing capacities with technical requirements led to the untimely and improper execution of leaching operations, which are an important agrotechnical measure for sown areas. [6. 75] This was of great importance for the lands of Khorezm, which were prone to salinization.

At the same time, the leadership of the union paid special attention to the development of not only cotton growing in the region, but also rice cultivation, which is a water-intensive branch of agriculture. In particular, the directives of the 23rd Congress of the CPSU on the plans for the development of the national economy of the USSR for 1966 – 1970 defined the task of establishing a large base for rice cultivation in the lower reaches of the Amu Darya. [5. 36-37] This decision subsequently had a significant impact on the hydrogeological system of the oasis, especially the distribution of water resources and the reclamation state of the lands.

The Tuyamuyun Reservoir, located in the lower reaches of the Amu Darya and being one of the main water facilities of the Uzbek SSR, was of great importance in providing water

and improving the land reclamation status of Khorezm. In 1969, a resolution of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of the Uzbek SSR and the Council of Ministers “On the Construction of the Tuyamuyun Reservoir on the Amu Darya” was adopted to utilize river water for irrigation and energy purposes. [1. 506] It consists of 4 large reservoirs with a water capacity of 7.8 billion m³, which were used to irrigate 0.7 million hectares of land and mainly for growing cotton. [6. 240] It should be noted that the Tuyamuyun Reservoir is a major hydraulic structure in Central Asia that supplied water to several regions of the Turkmen SSR.

As a result of the commissioning of the Tuyamuyun Reservoir, it became possible to provide the Kipchak-Arna, Jumaboy-Soka, and Sovet-yab irrigation systems, as well as the Lenin and Kizketgan canals, with stable water resources without the construction of a special dam at the Takhiatash Reservoir. This made it possible to increase the area of irrigated lands in the southern part of Khorezm by 300,000 hectares and to improve the water supply and reclamation status of irrigated lands in Khorezm and the southern part of the Karakalpak ASSR by 400,000 hectares. [7. 39]

In conclusion, it should be noted that the agrarian policy of the Soviet government in the region was aimed at absolute dominance of the cotton monoculture and maximizing the volume of raw material production. Therefore, the system of large irrigation and hydraulic structures built in the oasis, as well as plans for the development of land resources, directly served these priority areas of the agricultural sector. However, the long-term use of natural and water resources without considering environmental and economic consequences has led to a crisis in the hydrogeological system of the oasis, an increase in land salinity, and a profound disruption of the ecological balance in the region.

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